

North American Academic
Research | Volume 5 | Issue 4 |
April 2022 | Monthly Journal by
TWASP, USA | Impact Factor:
3.75 (2021)

North American Academic Research

Monthly peer reviewed Journal by **The
World Association of Scientists &
Professionals**
TWASP, United States

Methodological Comparison of Genomic Selection for Several Traits in Arabidopsis and Soybean

Medrine Mmayi Odinga^{1,2}, Jian-Ying Feng¹, Yuan-li Ni¹, Xiu-li Yue¹, Yuan-Ming Zhang³

¹Statistical Genomics Lab, College of Plant Science and Technology, Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuhan 430070, China

²Department of Mathematics, Egerton University, Egerton 536-20115, Kenya

³State Key Laboratory of Crop Genetics and Germplasm Enhancement, Nanjing Agricultural University, Nanjing 210095 / College of Plant Science and Technology, Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuhan 430070

Accepted April 29,2022

Published May 12,2022

Copyright: © The Author(s); **Conflicts of Interest:** There are no conflicts to declare.

Corresponding Author: Yuan-Ming Zhang. soyzhang@mail.hzau.edu.cn/ meldymmayi@gmail.com

Funding: This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (31571268), and Huazhong Agricultural University Scientific & Technological Self-innovation Foundation (Program No. 2014RC020).

How to cite this article: Medrine Mmayi Odinga, Jian-Ying Feng, Yuan-li Ni, Xiu-li Yue, Yuan-Ming Zhang (2022). Methodological Comparison of Genomic Selection for several traits in Arabidopsis and Soybean. *North American Academic Research*, 5(4), 295-320. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6539949>

ABSTRACT

Evidence from previous studies has confirmed the advantages of genomic selection (GS) in animal and plant breeding. Although many GS approaches are available, the knowledge about which is the best approach is limited. In this study, we evaluated six parametric and two non-parametric GS methods using the Arabidopsis datasets and soybean datasets with salt and water treatment in 2014 and 2015.

Cross-validation experiments, along with all markers and related markers at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels of significance in each of the datasets were carried out. Prediction accuracies were obtained, indicated by R^2 and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) between actual and predicted values, for all the methods in each dataset. As a result, the average R^2 across various traits and different numbers of related markers in Arabidopsis thaliana datasets for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were between 0.644 and 0.668, 0.700 suggesting that GBLUP and BLUP are the best GS approaches. The same trend was replicated in all the other datasets. EMMA model was used to estimate polygenic and residual variances. The average heritabilities for all markers and part of markers correlated at the 0.05 significance level were 0.758 and 0.741, 0.434 and 0.511 respectively, for *Arabidopsis thaliana*, soybean 2014 and 2015 water-treatment datasets. The same trend was repeated in salt treatment datasets. This indicates that using markers related to the trait can also capture the genetic variation in the natural population. In summary GBLUP, RKHS and BLUP are the superior GS approaches.

Keywords

Introduction

The research body has grown extensively since early descriptions of genomic prediction models (Nejati-Javaremi *et al.* 1997; Haley & Visscher 1998; Meuwissen *et al.* 2001). Genomic statistics is changing plant and animal breeding (Dekkers and Hospital 2002; Bernardo and Yu 2007; Hayes *et al.* 2009, VanRaden *et al.* 2009; Heffner *et al.* 2009; Calus 2010; Crossa *et al.* 2010; Daetwyler *et al.* 2010a ; Jannink *et al.* 2010; Wolc *et al.* 2011). Genomic prediction can increase the rates of genetic improvement through reduction of generation intervals, increased accuracy of estimated breeding values, and enhanced exploitation of available genetic resources through genome-guided mate choice (Sonesson *et al.* 2010; Schierenbeck *et al.* 2011; Pryce *et al.* 2012b). Genomic prediction uses all genetic markers to calculate the genomic estimated breeding values (GEBVs), it theoretically captures all of the loci that impact a trait. The genomic prediction potential accelerates crop improvement due to shorter generation times, and the avoidance of phenotypic evaluation as established by (Jannink *et al.* 2010). Genomic prediction revealed to outdo marker-assisted selection (MAS) where only a few diagnostic markers are used to follow up the inheritance of specific loci influencing a trait (Heffner *et al.* 2010). Also, marker-assisted recurrent selection (MARS) involves only a subset of significant markers used in selecting quantitative trait loci (QTL) in a particular population (Massman *et al.* 2013).

When (Meuwissen *et al.* 2001) associated the two Bayesian methods (BayesA and BayesB), in genomic predictions in an animal, BayesA and BayesB were able to predict the position of large QTL of the total genetic variance, but often did not identify the smaller QTL. There has been an increase in the procedures existing (Wang *et al.* 2012; de los Campos *et al.* 2013; Desta and Ortiz 2014) and pervasive uptake particularly in dairy cattle breeding where official GEBVs are available (<http://www.interbull.org>). These prediction methods, however, differ in their predictive capacity (de los Campos *et al.* 2013) and suitability for specific applications. Crop populations may require different prediction methods from animals due to the possible presence of extensive linkage disequilibrium (LD), population substructure and agronomic presentation traits that are frequently influenced by many QTL of the light result (Wimmer *et al.* 2013). Using simulated dataset centered on actual marker data from barley, RR-BLUP was shown to be more precise than BayesB (Zhong *et al.* 2009) and has been endorsed for crop enhancement applications (Heslot *et al.* 2012). Wimmer *et al.* 2013) associated the performance of four commonly used techniques; LASSO (Tibshirani 1996), RR-BLUP and BayesB (Meuwissen *et al.* 2001), and the elastic net (Zou and Hastie 2005). They found RR-BLUP superior to other methods endorsing it for use in crops. RR-BLUP has the benefit over Bayesian approaches of being easily implemented (de los Campos *et al.* 2013). In the prediction perspective, (de los Campos *et al.* 2010) used the statistic matrix G (or X) that can be eigen-decomposed as $G = UDU'$ with D containing the eigenvalues of G , and U being consistent eigenvectors. Recently, Gianola (2013) studied the impact of the prior on the posterior inference of special marker effects on the over-parameterized models used in genome

empowered prediction. He resolved that the primary driving force in the various Bayesian models is prior, not data; thus, different priors will produce different results because their shrinkage effect varies.

These studies evaluated several genomic prediction methods and identified the best technique with the high predictive ability and accuracy for the natural population. Here, we analyzed the prediction performance of six additive models (parametric) and two kernel models (non-parametric). Cross-validation with all markers (216130) and related markers at 0.05, 0.10, and 0.20 levels of significance was conducted respectively in *Arabidopsis*. Prediction accuracy was determined by Pearson's correlation between the fitted values and the observed values of the dependent variable. In our result, average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.644, 0.655, 0.668, 0.659, 0.680, 0.700, 0.656 and 0.694, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and BLUP are the best. The average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.219, 0.206, 0.200, 0.204, 0.220, 0.192, 0.168 and 0.196, respectively. It means that RKHS is the best GS approach. In the same way, cross-validation with all markers (106103) and related markers at 0.05, 0.10, and 0.20 levels of significance was conducted respectively in Soybean datasets. In our result for example soybean datasets with water treatment in 2014; average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.116, 0.103, 0.112, 0.106, 0.107, 0.115, 0.179 and 0.13, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and BayesA are the best GS approach. The average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.73, 0.721, 0.726, 0.718, 0.722, 0.653, 1.008 and 0.718, respectively. With salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 datasets; average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.083, 0.098, 0.091, 0.085, 0.147, 0.339, 0.163 and 0.106, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and RKHS are the best GS approach. The average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.337, 0.34, 0.361, 0.353, 0.323, 0.314, 0.355 and 0.342, respectively.

Materials and Methods

The Arabidopsis thaliana datasets

The well-known *Arabidopsis thaliana* datasets with 199 accessions each with 216130 SNPs (Atwell *et al.* 2010) were downloaded from <http://www.arabidopsis.usc.edu/> and re-analyzed in this study. Five quantitative traits analyzed were LN10, LN16, and LN22 (leaf number at a flowering time at 10 °C, 16 °C, and 22 °C, respectively), fresh and dry weights (FW and DW). For the five traits, missing individuals in the genotype and phenotype datasets were deleted respectively. Also, the SNPs with minor allele frequency <5% were deleted respectively. Thus, the SNPs for LN10, LN16, LN22, FW, and DW were 206295, 206203, 206322, 207702 and 207702, respectively. The phenotypes of lines for the above five traits were 177, 176, 176, 95 and 95, respectively. The STRUCTURE software version 1.0 under Linux system (<http://web.stanford.edu/group/pritchardlab/structure.html>) was used to calculate population structure.

The Soybean datasets

A total of 286 soybean cultivars from 6 geographic eco-types in China were obtained by stratified random sampling. The materials were planted in three-row plots measuring 1.5m wide and 2m long in a completely randomized design at Jiangpu experimental station, Nanjing Agricultural University, in 2014 and 2015. Approximately 0.3g of fresh leaves obtained from each cultivar in 2014 and 2015 was used to extract genomic DNA following the CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) method (Doyle *et al.* 1987). Salt tolerance was evaluated on five traits including the length of the main root (LR), the fresh and dry weights of roots (FWR and FDR), the biomass of seedlings (BS) and the length of hypocotyls (LH) of healthy seedlings after water solution treatments for approximately one week under greenhouse conditions. For the five traits, missing individuals in the genotype and phenotype datasets were deleted respectively. Also, the SNPs with minor allele frequency <5% were deleted respectively. The STRUCTURE software version 2.2 under Windows system (<http://web.stanford.edu/group/pritchardlab/structure.html>) was used to calculate population structure.

Heritability

Using efficient mixed-model association (EMMA) of Kang *et al.* (2008) implemented by R package EMMA (<http://mouse.cs.ucla.edu/emma/>), kinship matrix was incorporated into the mixed model framework to estimate additive (σ_a^2) and residual (σ_e^2) variances by restricted maximum log-likelihood (REML). The estimated variances were used to estimate heritability (h^2) as

$$h^2 = \frac{\sigma_a^2}{\sigma_a^2 + \sigma_e^2} \quad (1)$$

Genomic selection methods

BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS and BLUP implemented by the BGLR statistical package (<https://r-forge.r-project.org/projects/bglr/>) in R (Pérez & de los Campos 2014) were compared in this study using the well-known *Arabidopsis thaliana* datasets and Soybean datasets. Here, the number of markers was also investigated. The number of all the markers was 216130 (*Arabidopsis*); 106013 (soybean), and parts of markers correlated the traits under study at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels of significance were considered.

Bayesian Methods Bayes theorem is used to syndicate prior beliefs of marker effects, which are expressed regarding prior distributions, with information from data for inference. Thus, Bayesian multiple-regression models simultaneously fit much more markers than the number of observations available for the analysis. Often, the analyses are too complicated for closed-form solutions, and Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) sampling is used to conclude posterior distributions.

For a continuous response, $(y_i, i = 1, \dots, n)$ the data equation was represented as $y_i = \eta_i + \varepsilon_i$, where η_i is a linear predictor (the expected value of y_i given predictors) and ε_i are independent normal model residuals with mean zero and variance $w_i^2 \sigma_\varepsilon^2$. Here, the w_i 's are weights and σ_ε^2 is residual variance. In matrix notation we have

$$y = \eta + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where $y = \{y_1, \dots, y_n\}$, $\eta = \{\eta_1, \dots, \eta_n\}$ and $\varepsilon = \{\varepsilon_1, \dots, \varepsilon_n\}$.

The predictor represented the conditional expectation function, was written as follows:

$$\eta = 1\mu + \sum_j X_j \beta_j + \sum_l u_l \quad (3)$$

where μ is an intercept, X_j are design matrices for predictors, $X_j = \{x_{ijk}\}$, β_{jk} are vectors of effects associated with the columns of X_j and $u_l = \{u_{l1}, \dots, u_{ln}\}$ are vectors of random effects. Collecting the above assumptions, we used the following likelihood

$$p(y | \theta) = \prod_{i=1}^n N(y_i | \mu + \sum_j \sum_{k=1}^{K_j} x_{ijk} \beta_{jk} + \sum_l u_{li}, \sigma_\varepsilon^2 w_i^2) \quad (4)$$

where θ represents the collection of unknowns; the intercept, regression coefficients, random effects, and residual variance.

BLUP estimation: BLUP was evaluated by the model

$$y = \mu 1_n + \sum_i X_i g_i + e \quad (5)$$

where the summation \sum_i is over all segments. In this study, we set the error variance $= I$. The estimation of g_i is obtained from mixed-model equations (Henderson 1984).

BayesA With Bayesian estimate, the data are modeled at two levels (Meuwissen *et al.* 2001). In the first level of the hierarchy, marker effects were allocated normal densities with zero mean and marker-specific variance parameters $\sigma_{\beta_{jk}}^2$. In the second level of the hierarchy, these variance parameters were assigned IID scaled-inverse Chi-squared densities with a degree of freedom and scale parameters df_β and S_β , respectively. The model at the level of the data is equal to that with BLUP estimation except that the variances of the segments are $\text{var}(g_{ij}) = \sigma_{gi}^2$, which are different for every part estimated by the model for the variances of the

segments. The prior distribution of variations of segments was the scaled- t density, with parameters df_β and S_β in this model (Meuwissen *et al.* 2001). In this study, the level of freedom parameter was regarded as known; we set $df_\beta = 5$. The approach and coefficient of variation (CV) of the gamma density were Mode (S_β) = $(S - 1) / r = r$ (for $s > 1$) and $CV(S_0) = 1/\sqrt{s}$. We set $s = 1.1$.

BayesB Marker effects are assigned in a scaled- t density (BayesB) in these models (Habier *et al.* 2011). The genetic variances across loci are that there are many loci with no genetic variance and a few with genetic variation. However, the prior density of method BayesA does not have a density peak at $\sigma_{gi}^2 = 0$. BayesB uses a prior that has a high density π at $\sigma_{gi}^2 = 0$ and has an inverted chi-square distribution for $\sigma_{gi}^2 > 0$. This parameter was treated as unknown and was assigned a Beta prior $\pi \sim Beta(p_0, \pi_0)$, with $p_0 > 0$ and $\pi_0 \in [0, 1]$. This beta prior was parameterized in a way that the expected value by $E(\pi) = \pi_0$; on the other hand, p_0 was interpreted as the number of prior counts, the variance of the Beta distribution was then given by, which was inversely proportional to p_0 . Choosing $p_0 = 2$ and $\pi_0 = 0.5$ provided a uniform prior to the interval $[0, 1]$ in this study.

BayesC Marker effects are assigned in a scaled- t density BayesC (Habier *et al.* 2011). In this method, the SNP effects have a common variance, which follows a scaled inverse with prior parameters df_β and S_β . As a result, the effect of an SNP fitted with probability $(1 - \pi)$ follows a mixture of multivariate Student's t -distributions where π is the probability of a marker having zero effect. Parameters df_β and S_β were chosen as described for BayesA. The π parameter is treated as an unknown with a uniform $(0, 1)$ prior distribution.

Bayesian LASSO (BL) In the BLASSO of Park and Casella (2008), the marginal distribution of marker effects was double-exponential. In the first level, marker effects were assigned independent average densities with null mean and maker-specific variance parameter $\tau_{jk}^2 \sigma_\epsilon^2$. The residual variance was assigned a scaled inverse Chi-square density, and the marker-specific scale parameters τ_{jk}^2 were assigned IID exponential densities with rate parameter $\lambda^2 / 2$. Finally, the last level of the hierarchy λ^2 , BGLR set type='gamma' and $s = 1.1$, and solved for the scale parameter to match the expected R-squared of the model.

Bayesian Ridge Regression (BRR) When the BRR option was selected, regression coefficients were allocated normal IID normal distributions, with mean zero and variance σ_β^2 (Meuwissen *et al.* 2001). In the 2nd level of the hierarchy, the variance parameter was assigned a scaled inverse Chi-square density, with parameters df_β and S_β . The density was parameterized in a way that the previous predictable value and mode

are $E(\sigma_\beta^2) = \frac{S_\beta}{df_\beta - 2}$ and mode $\sigma_\beta^2 = \frac{S_\beta}{df_\beta + 2}$, respectively. In this study, $df_\beta = 5$. An analysis with fixed variance parameter was attained by choosing the degree of freedom constraint to a significant value (10^{-10}) and solving for the scale using $S_\beta = \sigma_\beta^2 \times (df_\beta + 2)$; this gave a prior that collapses to the point of mass at σ_β^2 .

GBLUP (Genomic best linear unbiased prediction) GBLUP utilizes genomic relationships to estimate the genetic merit of an individual (VanRaden 2008; Habier *et al.* 2011). GBLUP is useful in the assessment of variance components and genomic heritabilities. The GBLUP combines genomic information into BLUP by using the genomic relationship matrix (GRM) as a substitute for the numerator relationship matrix.

The GBLUP model used as

$$y = Xb + Zg + e \quad (6)$$

where y is a vector of phenotypes, X is a design matrix relating the fixed effects to each subject, b is a vector of fixed effects, Z is a design matrix allocating records to genetic values, g is a vector of additive effects for an individual, and e is a vector of random normal deviates with variance. Furthermore, $\text{var}(g) = G\sigma_g^2$ where G is the genomic relationship matrix, and σ_g^2 is the genetic variation of this model. In the previous studies, the GBLUP was based on a single linear kernel (Xu 2013a).

Reproducing Kernel Hilbert Spaces Regressions (RKHS) RKHS have been used for regression smoothing spline (Wahba 1990), spatial smoothing (Kriging Cressie 1988), classification problems support vector machine (Vapnik 1998), and genomic prediction Gianola *et al.* (2006). In genomic prediction, several methodological and applied articles were published (Gianola and de los Campos 2008; Gonzalez-Recio *et al.* 2008; de los Campos *et al.* 2009a, 2010).

RKHS regression was represented as follows:

$$\begin{cases} y = 1\mu + u + \varepsilon \\ p(\mu, u, \varepsilon) \propto N(u; 0, \mathbf{K}\sigma_u^2) N(\varepsilon; 0, \mathbf{I}\sigma_\varepsilon^2) \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

de los Campos *et al.* (2009) where $K = \{K(x_i, x_i')\}$ is a $n \times n$ kinship matrix. The structure of the model described by (5) is of the standard mixed model (Quaas and Pollak 1980), and the pedigree-derived numerator relationship matrix (A) is replaced by the kinship matrix (K).

Measurement of prediction accuracy

Pearson correlation (r) between actual and predicted observations was used to measure prediction accuracy in five-fold cross-validation experiments. The perfect correlation was achieved when $r = 1.0$. The prediction accuracy was defined by [Lehermeier et al. \(2013\)](#) as

$$\text{Accuracy} = r / \sqrt{h^2} \quad (8)$$

Measurement of prediction error

The predictive error was measured by R^2 , mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE) and root MSE (RMSE) ([Hastie et al. 2005](#); [Daetwyler et al. 2013](#)), which are defined as follows.

R^2 was defined as

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{SS_e}{SS_T} \quad (9)$$

where $SS_e = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$ and $SS_T = \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2$. Average R^2 over seven traits was calculated. Large R^2 indicates small prediction error.

Mean absolute error (MAE) MAE was defined by

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (10)$$

The smaller MAE value is, the better the prediction accuracy is.

Mean squared error (MSE) MSE was defined by

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \quad (11)$$

The smaller MSE value is, the better the prediction accuracy is. The perfect fit was achieved when $MSE = 0$.

Root mean squared error (RMSE) RMSE was defined as $RMSE = \sqrt{MSE}$. The smaller the RMSE, the better the prediction accuracy is.

Cross-validation experiments

199 Arabidopsis accessions and 286 soybean cultivars were divided into five groups. Among the five groups, four groups were used to estimate parameters, such as marker effects β , polygenic variance ϕ , and residual variance σ_e^2 . These parameter estimates along with marker information of the left group were used to predict the phenotypic values in the remainder group ([Xu et al. 2014](#)).

Results

Heritability estimated with associated traits at various significant levels

***Arabidopsis thaliana* datasets** First, all the SNPs were used to calculate the kinship matrix K. This K matrix was incorporated into the mixed model to estimate polygenic and residual variances for each trait.

The two variances were used to estimate heritability. As a result, the heritabilities for LD, LDV, SD, SDV, FT10, FT16, and FT22 were between 0.720 and 0.776, with the mean of 0.758. Second, part markers that are correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance were used to calculate the kinship matrix K.

In the same way, the corresponding heritabilities were estimated. As a result, the heritabilities for the above seven traits were between 0.693 and 0.767, with the mean of 0.741. This result also shows that using markers associated with the trait can also capture genetic variation in a natural population (Tables 1).

Soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2014 and 2015

Similarly, using water as a control factor, all the SNPs were used to calculate the kinship matrix K in the first step. This K matrix was incorporated into the mixed model to estimate polygenic and residual variances for each trait. The two variances were used to estimate heritability. As a result, the heritabilities for LR, LH, FWR, DWR, and BS with the water treatment in 2014 were between 0.368 and 0.504, with the mean of 0.434. The heritabilities in soybean datasets with water treatment in 2015 were between 0.387 and 0.531, with the mean of 0.468 (Table 2). Second, part of the markers that are correlated with the traits at 0.05 level of significance was used to calculate the kinship matrix K. In the same way, the corresponding heritabilities were estimated. As a result, the heritabilities for the above five traits in 2014 and 2015 with the water treatment were between 0.40 and 0.661, with the mean of 0.511, and 0.509 and 0.639, with the mean of 0.585 respectively (Table 2). Thus, using markers associated with the trait can also capture genetic variation in a natural population.

Prediction accuracies for various numbers of markers

Prediction accuracy was estimated by the correlation between the predicted and observed phenotypic values standardized with the square root of the heritability, that is, $r/\sqrt{h^2}$ (Lehermeier *et al.* 2013). As a result, using *Arabidopsis thaliana* datasets, the accuracies for LD, LDV, SD, SDV, FT10, FT16, and FT22 were between 0.695 and 1.018, with the mean of 0.866. Secondly, part of the markers that are correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance was used to calculate the accuracy similarly. As a result, the accuracies for the above seven traits were between 0.904 and 1.07, with the mean of 1.000. This result shows that using markers associated with the trait can also achieve higher accuracy than all the markers in a natural population (Table 1). Analyzing accuracies for the five quantitative traits LR, LH, FWR, DWR, and BS in soybean datasets with water treatment in 2014, were between 0.210 and 1.226, with the mean of 0.57, and for the water treatment in

2015 were between 1.216 and 1.283, with the mean of 1.246 (Table 2). Using part of the markers that are correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance were used to calculate the accuracy in the same way. As a result, the accuracies for the above five traits with water treatment in 2014 were between 0.079 and 0.777, with the mean of 0.526. Similarly, with water treatment in 2015, the accuracies for the above five traits were between 0.655 and 1.060, with the mean of 0.834 (Table 2).

This result shows that using markers associated with the trait can also achieve higher accuracy than all the markers in a natural population.

Soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 and 2015

Using salt tolerance as a control in Soybean. First, all the SNPs were used to calculate the kinship matrix K in the first step. This K matrix was incorporated into the mixed model to estimate polygenic and residual variances for each trait. The two variances were used to estimate heritability. As a result, the heritabilities for LR, LH, FWR, DWR, and BS for soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 were between 0.335 and 0.496, with the mean of 0.409. The heritabilities with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015 datasets were between 0.398 and 0.573, with the mean of 0.481 (Table 3). Secondly, part of the markers that are correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance was used to calculate the kinship matrix K. In the same way, the corresponding heritabilities were estimated. As a result, the heritabilities for the above five traits with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 were between 0.437 and 0.661, with the mean of 0.502, and in 2015 the heritabilities were between 0.551 and 0.792, with the mean of 0.613 (Table 3).

Thus, using markers associated with the trait can also capture genetic variation in a natural population.

Accuracies for the five quantitative traits LR, LH, FWR, DWR, and BS in soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment were between 1.15 and 1.44, with the mean of 1.28, and for the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015 datasets were between 1.06 and 1.442, with the mean of 1.182 (Table 3). Markers correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance were used to calculate the accuracy in the same way. As a result, the accuracies for the above five traits for the salt (NaCl) treatment were between 0.316 and 0.912, with the mean of 0.658. Similarly, with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015, the accuracies for the above five traits were between 0.287 and 0.676, with the mean of 0.494. This result also shows that using markers associated with the trait can also achieve higher accuracy than all the markers in a natural population (Table 3)

Prediction accuracies for various methods

In each of eight approaches, first, 5-fold cross-validation experiments along with all the SNPs were carried out. Once all the predicted phenotypic values were obtained Pearson's correlation was computed.

Using Arabidopsis thaliana datasets;

The average correlation coefficients across traits for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BLASSO, BRR, RKHS, GBLUP, and BLUP were 0.732, 0.754, 0.777, 0.745, 0.736, 0.755, 0.749 and 0.759, respectively, indicating the best one being BayesC, followed by BLUP. If we used only part of markers, for example, the markers correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance, the best GS approach was RKHS (0.868), and the next one was BayesC (0.865). At the 0.10 level, the best one was BLUP (0.871), and the next was GBLUP (0.858). At 0.20 level, the same trend was observed (BLUP: 0.846; GBLUP: 0.844), (Figure 1).

Soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2014 and 2015

Analyzing the soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2014, the average correlation coefficients across traits for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.126, 0.166, 0.218, 0.188, 0.126, 0.373, 0.285 and 0.178, respectively, indicating the best one of GBLUP, followed by RKHS. If we used only part of markers, for example, the markers correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance, the best one was GBLUP (0.385) followed by BayesA (0.369). Under the 0.10 level of significance, the best one was GBLUP (0.421) followed by BLASSO (0.403). At 0.20 level, the same trend was observed (BLUP: 0.436; GBLUP: 0.365), (Figure 2).

In summary, the average correlations across various significant levels indicated that the best three methods for GS were GBLUP (0.386), BLUP (0.327) and RKHS (0.308).

Similarly, soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2015, the average correlation coefficients across traits for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.321, 0.253, 0.323, 0.354, 0.305, 0.851, 0.263 and 0.305, respectively, indicating the best one of GBLUP, followed by BRR. If we used only part of markers, for example, the markers correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance, the best one was BayesB (0.640) followed by BLUP (0.612). At the 0.10 level, the best one was BRR (0.687) followed by BayesC (0.646). At 0.20 level, the same trend was observed (BLUP: 0.627; BLASSO: 0.623), (Figure 3).

In summary, the average correlations across various significant levels indicated that the best three GS methods were GBLUP (0.646), BRR (0.556) and BLUP (0.537).

Soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 and 2015

Analyzing the soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014, the average correlation coefficients across traits for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.142, 0.15, 0.159, 0.125, 0.127, 0.816, 0.231 and 0.153, respectively, indicating the best GS approach is GBLUP, followed by RKHS. If we used only part of markers, for example, the markers correlated with the traits at the

0.05 level of significance, the best one was GBLUP (0.47) followed by BLASSO (0.386). At the 0.10 level, the best one was GBLUP (0.483) followed by RKHS (0.458). While at 0.20 level, a similar trend was observed (BLASSO: 0.449; GBLUP: 0.423), (Figure 4).

In summary, the average correlations across various significant levels indicated that the best three methods for GS were GBLUP (0.473), BLASSO (0.319) and RKHS (0.295).

Prediction errors for various methods

Arabidopsis thaliana datasets;

The average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.644, 0.655, 0.668, 0.659, 0.680, 0.700, 0.656 and 0.694, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and BLUP are the best GS approaches. Similarly, the average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.219, 0.206, 0.200, 0.220, 0.204, 0.168, 0.192 and 0.196, respectively. It means that the best three methods for GS were RKHS, GBLUP, and BLUP. (Table 4; Figure 1). Thus, the best GS approaches across various indicators are RKHS and GBLUP

Soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2014 and 2015

For the soybean dataset with the water treatment in 2014. Average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.116, 0.103, 0.112, 0.107, 0.106, 0.179, 0.115 and 0.130, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and BLUP are the best. It shows that RKHS and BLUP are the best (Table 5; Figure 2). Thus, the best approaches across various indicators are RKHS, GBLUP, and BLUP.

With the water treatment in soybean datasets in 2015. Similarly, average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.246, 0.288, 0.299, 0.334, 0.293, 0.426, 0.239 and 0.300, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and BRR are the best GS approaches. In the same way, the average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.748, 0.691, 0.726, 0.687, 0.736, 0.669, 0.675 and 0.710, respectively. It means that GBLUP and RKHS are the best (Table 5; Figure 3). In summary, the best approaches for GS across various indicators are GBLUP and RKHS.

Soybean datasets with salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 and 2015

For the soybean datasets with salt treatment in 2014, average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.083, 0.098, 0.091, 0.085, 0.147, 0.339, 0.163 and 0.106, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and RKHS are the best GS approaches. Similarly, the average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.337, 0.340, 0.361, 0.353, 0.323, 0.314, 0.355 and 0.342, respectively. It implies that the best three GS methods are GBLUP, BLASSO, and

BLUP. (Table 6; Figure 4). Thus, the best GS approaches across various indicators are GBLUP, RKHS, and BLASSO.

With the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015, the average R^2 across various traits and various numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP were 0.066, 0.054, 0.046, 0.074, 0.13, 0.298, 0.108 and 0.083, respectively, suggesting that GBLUP and RKHS are the best GS approaches. In a similar way, the average MAE for the above eight methods were 0.586, 0.595, 0.561, 0.585, 0.56, 0.544, 0.538 and 0.551, respectively. It implies that GBLUP and RKHS are the best. (Table 6; Figure 5). Thus, the best GS approaches across various indicators are GBLUP and RKHS in this case.

Discussion

Model predictability is represented by the correlation coefficient between the observed and the predicted phenotypic values (Xu *et al.* 2014). In this study, all the correlation coefficients for the above seven traits were more than 0.70, which is higher than that in Xu *et al.* (2014). Meanwhile, accuracies for the seven traits were between 0.695 and 1.00 while using all SNPs. If part markers correlated with the traits at the 0.05 level of significance were used, accuracies for the seven traits were between 0.904 and 1.00. These accuracies are also higher than 0.500 in wheat (Heffner *et al.* 2010) and maize (Longin *et al.* 2015). Similar results were noted in prediction accuracy for wheat resistance to yellow and stem rust as being influenced by their low and high heritability, respectively (Ornella *et al.* 2012). Also, results for grain yield estimated the accuracy of 0.580 (low heritability) versus grain moisture accuracy of 0.900 (high heritability) in maize respectively (Zhao *et al.* 2013). High prediction accuracy was observed in this study. Results in Table 1, 2 & 3 showed that all the traits used in this study have high heritabilities. If we integrate prediction accuracy with trait heritability, it is reasonable to suppose that high accuracy in this study is derived from high heritability. Prediction accuracies in *Arabidopsis thaliana* are significantly different from those in soybean. For example; higher accuracy values greater than 0.9 were observed (0.904, 0.993) in *Arabidopsis thaliana* unlike in soybean datasets (0.777, 0.673). It displayed higher heritability traits used in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Table 1 & 2) and low heritability traits used in soybean (Table 3) datasets.

Significant differences in R^2 values in the three datasets are observed. Very high R^2 values for example (0.700, 0.694) are observed in *Arabidopsis thaliana* datasets which are due to the high heritabilities traits used unlike in the soybean datasets very low R^2 values (0.116, 0.103) are observed. Integrating R^2 values with trait heritability, it is reasonable to suppose that the high R^2 values in this study are derived from high heritability. The objective of the current study was to compare all the eight methods. Owing to high heritabilities values observed in this study, more inheritance information would likely be captured by these approaches. Thus, by extension, it is expected that the evaluated methods would have higher accuracy.

Based on the results of the current study, the best approaches across various indicators using different marker sizes in both the datasets (Arabidopsis and Soybean) are RKHS and GBLUP. The efficiency of the kernel and additive methods on two wheat traits across several environments was compared by Pérez-Rodríguez *et al.* (2012) who showed RKHS was the best method to predict days to heading. Zhong *et al.* (2009) similarly reported that GBLUP and BayesB are each best suited to different barley traits.

Our results are similar to these previous results showing RKHS and GBLUP as the best predictive models. Jarquín *et al.* (2014) extended the GBLUP model to incorporate environmental covariates, highly dimensional markers, and their interactions into random effects models. This was similar to our study which incorporated two different environmental factors in the soybean datasets in 2014 and 2015. For the soybean data population, 5% related markers can provide a consistent prediction while higher density genotyping provides only marginal gains in predictive ability. This result is likely associated with soybean's genomic properties, such as the uneven distribution of markers in soybean genome (Li *et al.* 2014) and the existence of significant disequilibrium blocks (Hyten *et al.* 2007), which is similar to our results. In kernel models, markers are informative regardless of whether they are linked to any quantitative trait loci (Habier *et al.* 2007) whereas null effect markers would harm any additive model incapable of performing the efficient variable selection. Our results indicate kernel models had a variable selection term, thus, provided better predictions.

In plant breeding, the most economically important trait is grain yield, which is significantly affected by environmental factors like soil alkalinity and salinity, as well as by genotype*environment interaction (G*E). The impact of the number of markers on accuracy decreases as more SNPs are used. Several studies have stated the importance of relatedness measures on genomic prediction accuracy (Habier *et al.* 2007; Clark *et al.* 2011a, 2012; Pszczola *et al.* 2012). The effect of relatedness on accuracy was shown by German Holstein cattle by grouping individuals into different groups according to their maximum relatedness and evaluating accuracy within each cluster (Habier *et al.* 2010). However, traits with high relatedness to the reference are always expected to have greater accuracy over distantly related traits (Habier *et al.* 2007; Hayes *et al.* 2009d; Goddard 2009). Previous studies on plant populations (Lorenzana *et al.* 2009; Heffner *et al.* 2011; Hickey *et al.* 2014; Zhang *et al.* 2015) approximated one thousand markers were required before the prediction accuracy plateaued. These were similar to our results in that; related population size had the greatest impact on accuracy. Prediction accuracies were higher for a marker number associated with the trait datasets at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels of significance in contrast to all marker dataset. Thus, for high prediction accuracy in a natural population, the marker number and relatedness of markers is a major factor to be considered. It's thus economically viable to use fewer marker than a whole set while still achieving similar results. Therefore, plant breeding programs seeking high accuracy in genomic prediction should best allocate resources by investing in part of markers instead of using all markers. However, further research is needed in determining the projection marker number levels of this relatedness.

Conclusion

We evaluated six parametric and two non-parametric GS methods using seven flowering time-related traits in *Arabidopsis thaliana*, soybean datasets with salt and water treatments in 2014 and 2015. Cross-validation experiments, along with all markers and related markers at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels of significance, were carried out to obtain prediction accuracies indicated by R^2 and MAE between actual and predicted values for all the methods. As a result, average R^2 across various traits and different numbers of related markers for BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BRR, BLASSO, GBLUP, RKHS, and BLUP ranged between 0.644 and 0.700, suggesting that GBLUP and BLUP are the two superior GS methods. The average MAE for the above eight methods ranged between 0.168 and 0.219. It implies that RKHS and GBLUP are the best GS approaches in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. The same trend was replicated in all the other datasets. The average heritabilities for all markers and part of markers correlated at the 0.05 level for were 0.758 and 0.741, 0.434 and 0.511, 0.468 and 0.585, for *Arabidopsis thaliana* and soybean datasets with water treatment 2014 and 2015 respectively, while with salt treatment in 2014 and 2015 were 0.409 and 0.502, 0.481 and 0.613 respectively. In summary GBLUP, RKHS and BLUP are the superior GS approaches.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by the National Natural Science Foundation of China (31571268), and Huazhong Agricultural University Scientific & Technological Self-innovation Foundation (Program No. 2014RC020).

Author Contributions

Y.-M.Z. conceived and supervised the study and revised the manuscript. M.M.O performed the experiments and analyzed the data and wrote the draft. All the authors read, revised and approved the final manuscript.

References

- 1 Nejadi-Javaremi A, Smith C, Gibson JP. Effect of total allelic relationship on accuracy of evaluation and response to selection. *J Anim Sci.* 75(7), 1738-1745 (1997).
- 2 Haley CS, Visscher PM. Strategies to utilize marker-quantitative trait loci associations. *J Dairy Sci.* 81 Suppl 2, 85-89 (1998).
- 3 Meuwissen THE, Hayes BJ, Goddard ME. Prediction of total genetic value using genome-wide dense marker maps. *Genetics.* 157, 1819–1829 (2001).
- 4 Dekkers JCM, Hospital F. The use of molecular genetics in the improvement of agricultural populations. *Nat Rev Genet.* 3, 22–32 (2002).
- 5 Bernardo R, Yu J. Prospects for genomewide selection for quantitative traits in maize. *Crop Sci.* 47,1082–1090 (2007).
- 6 Hayes BJ, Bowman PJ, Chamberlain AJ, Goddard ME. Genomic selection in dairy cattle: progress and challenges. *J Dairy Sci.* 92(2), 433-443 (2009).

- 7 Van Raden PM, DaSilva M, Sullivan P. National and international genomic evaluation in dairy cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 92(E-Suppl. 1), 175 (Abstr. 200) (2009).
- 8 Heffner EL, Jannink JL, Sorrells ME. Genomic selection for crop improvement. *Crop Sci.* 49, 1–12 (2009).
- 9 Calus MPL. Genomic breeding value prediction methods and procedures. *Animal.* 4,157–164 (2010).
- 10 Crossa J, Gianola D, de los Campos G, Pérez P, Burgueño J, Araus JL, Makumbi D, Singh RP, Dreisigacker S, Yan J, Arief V, Banziger M, Braun HJ. Prediction of genetic values of quantitative traits in plant breeding using pedigree and molecular markers. *Genetics.* 186,713–724 (2010).
- 11 Daetwyler HD, Henshall JM, Hickey JM, Dominik S, Gredler B. The accuracy of estimated genomic breeding values for wool and meat traits in a multi-breed sheep population. *Animal Prod Sci.* 50,1004–1010 (2010).
- 12 Jannink JL, Lorenz AJ, Iwata H. Genomic selection in plant breeding: from theory to practice. *Brief Funct Genomics.* 9(2), 166-177 (2010).
- 13 Anna Wolc, Chris Stricker, Jesus Arango, Petek Settar, Janet E Fulton, Neil P O'Sullivan, Rudolf Preisinger, David Habier, Rohan Fernando, Dorian J Garrick, Susan J Lamont, Jack CM Dekkers. Breeding value prediction for production traits in layer chickens using pedigree or genomic relationships in a reduced animal model. *Genet Sel Evol.* 43(1), 5 (2011).
- 14 Sonesson AK, Woolliams JA, Meuwissen THE. Maximizing genetic gain while controlling rates of genomic inbreeding using genomic optimum contribution selection, in Proceedings of the 9th World Congress on Genetics Applied to Livestock Production. German Society for Animal Science. 892–895 (2010).
- 15 Schierenbeck S, Pimentel EC, Tietze M, Körte J, Reents R, Reinhardt F, Simianer H, König S. Controlling inbreeding and maximizing genetic gain using semi-definite programming with pedigree-based And genomic relationships. *J Dairy Sci.* 94, 6143–6152 (2011).
- 16 Pryce, JE, Hayes BJ, Goddard ME. Novel strategies to minimize progeny inbreeding while maximizing genetic gain using genomic information. *J Dairy Sci.* 95, 377–388 (2012).
- 17 Heffner EL, Lorenz AJ, Jannink JL, and Sorrells ME. Plant breeding with the genomic selection: gain per unit time and cost. *Crop Sci.* 50, 1681-1690 (2010).
- 18 Massman JM, Jung HJG, and Bernardo R. Genomewide selection versus marker-assisted recurrent selection to improve grain yield and stover quality traits for cellulosic ethanol in maize. *Crop Sci.* 53, 58-66 (2013).
- 19 Wang CL, Ma PP, Zhang Z, Ding XD, Liu JF, Fu WX, Weng ZQ, Zhang Q. Comparison of five methods for genomic breeding value estimation for the common dataset of the 15th QTLMAS workshop. *BMC Proc;* 6(Suppl2), S13 (2012).
- 20 de Los Campos G, Perez P. BGLR: Bayesian Generalized Regression R package, version 1.0." R package version 1.0, 2013.URL <https://r-forge.r-project.org/projects/bglr/>
- 21 Desta ZA, Ortiz R. Genomic selection: genome-wide prediction in plant improvement. *Trends Plant Sci.* 19(9), 592-601 (2014).
- 22 Wimmer V, Lehermeier C, Albrecht T, Auinger HJ, Wang Y, Schön CC. Genome-wide prediction of traits with different genetic architecture through efficient variable selection. *Genetics.* 195, 573-587 (2013).
- 23 Zhong S, Dekker J, Fernando R, Jannink JL. Factors affecting accuracy from genomic selection in populations derived from multiple inbred lines: a Barley case study. *Genetics.* 182, 355-364 (2009).
- 24 Heslot N, Yang HP, Sorrells M, Jannink JL. Genomic selection in plant breeding: A comparison of models. *Crop Sci.* 52, 146-160 (2012).

- 25 Tibshirani R. Regression shrinkage, and selection via the LASSO. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society Series B.* 58, 267-288 (1996).
- 26 Zou H, and Hastie T. Regularization and variable selection via the elastic net. *Journal of Royal Statistical Society* 67, 301-320 (2005).
- 27 de los Campos G, Gianola D, Rosa GJ, Weigel KA, Crossa J. Semi-parametric genomic-enabled prediction of genetic values using reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces methods. *Genetics Research.* 92(04), 295-308 (2010).
- 28 Gianola D. Priors in whole-genome regression; The Bayesian alphabet returns. *Genetics.* 194, 573–596 (2013).
- 29 Atwell S, Huang YS, Vilhjálmsson BJ, Willems G, Horton M, Li Y, Meng D, Platt A, Tarone AM, Hu TT, Jiang R, Mulyati NW, Zhang X, Amer MA, Baxter I, Brachi B, Chory J, Dean C, Debieu M, de Meaux J, Ecker JR, Faure N, Kniskern JM, Jones JD, Michael T, Nemri A, Roux F, Salt DE, Tang C, Todesco M, Traw MB, Weigel D, Marjoram P, Borevitz JO, Bergelson J, Nordborg M. Genome-wide association study of 107 phenotypes in *Arabidopsis thaliana* inbred lines. *Nature.* 465(7298), 627-631 (2010).
- 30 Kang HM, Zaitlen NA, Wade CM, Kirby A, Heckerman D, Daly MJ, Eskin E. Efficient control of population structure in model organism association mapping. *Genetics.* 178(3), 1709- 1723 (2008).
- 31 Pérez P, de los Campos G. Genome-wide regression, and prediction with the BGLR statistical package. *Genetics.* 198(2), 483-495 (2014).
- 32 Henderson CR. *Applications of Linear Models in Animal Breeding.* University of Guelph, Guelph, Ontario, Canada (1984).
- 33 Habier D, Fernando RL, Kizilkaya K, Garrick DJ. Extension of the Bayesian alphabet for genomic selection. *BMC Bioinformatics.* 12(1), 186 (2011).
- 34 Park T, Casella G. The Bayesian Lasso. *Journal of the American Statistical Associations.* 103(482), 681-686 (2008).
- 35 VanRaden PM. Efficient methods to compute genomic predictions. *Journal of dairy science.* 91(11), 4414-4423 (2008).
- 36 Xu S. Mapping quantitative trait loci by controlling polygenic background effects. *Genetics.* 195(4), 1209-1222 (2013).
- 37 Wahba G. *Spline models for observational data.* Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics. 153-169 (1990).
- 38 Cressie N. *Spatial Prediction, and Ordinary Kriging: Mathematical Geology, V. 20.* Springer Link. 405-421 (1988).
- 39 Vapnik V. *Statistical learning theory.* Wiley (1998).
- 40 Gianola D, Fernando RL, Stella A. Genomic-assisted Prediction of Genetic Values with Semi-parametric Procedures. *Genetics.* 173(3), 1761-1776 (2006).
- 41 Gianola D, van Kaam JB. Reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces regression methods for genomic assisted prediction of quantitative traits. *Genetics.* 178(4), 2289-2303 (2008).
- 42 González-Recio O, Gianola D, Long N, Weigel KA, Rosa GJ, Avendaño S. Non-parametric methods for incorporating genomic information into genetic evaluations: an application to mortality in broilers. *Genetics.* 178(4), 2305-2313 (2008).
- 43 de los Campos G, Naya H, Gianola D, Crossa J, Legarra A, Manfredi E, Weigel K, Cotes JM. Predicting quantitative traits with regression models for dense molecular markers and pedigree. *Genetics.* 182(1), 375-385 (2009).
- 44 Quaas RL, Pollak EJ. *Advances in Statistical Methods for Genetics Improvement of Livestock.* Springer-Verlag (1990).
- 45 Lehermeier C, Wimmer V, Albrecht T, Auinger HJ, Gianola D, Schmid VJ, Schön CC. Sensitivity to prior specification in Bayesian genome-based prediction models. *Statistical applications in genetics and molecular biology. Stat Appl Genet Mol Biol.* 12(3), 375-391 (2013).
- 46 Hastie T, Tibshirani R, Franklin J, Friedman J. *The elements of statistical learning: data mining, inference, and prediction.* The Mathematical Intelligencer. 27(2), 83-85 (2005).

- 47 Daetwyler HD, Calus MP, Pong-Wong R, de Los Campos G, Hickey JM. Genomic prediction in animals and plants: simulation of data, validation, reporting, and benchmarking. *Genetics*. 193, 347–365 (2013).
- 48 Xu S, Zhu D, Zhang Q. Predicting hybrid performance in rice using genomic best linear unbiased prediction. *Proc Natl Acad Sci*. 111, 12456-12461 (2014).
- 49 Longin CFH, Mi XF, Wurschum T. Genomic selection in wheat: optimum allocation of test resources and comparison of breeding strategies for line and hybrid breeding. *Theor Appl Genet*. 128(7), 1297–1306 (2015).
- 50 Leonardo Ornella L, Sukhwinder Singh, Perez P, Burgueno J, Singh RP, Tapia E, Bhavani S, Dreisigacker S, Braun HJ, Mathews KL, Crossa J. Genomic prediction of genetic values for resistance to wheat rusts. *Plant Genome* 5, 136-148 (2012).
- 51 Zhao Y, Zeng J, Fernando R, Reif CJ. Genomic prediction of hybrid wheat performance. *Crop Sci*. 53(3), 802-810 (2013).
- 52 Pérez-Rodríguez P, Gianola D, González-Camacho JM, Crossa J, Manès Y, Dreisigacker S. Comparison between linear and non-parametric regression models for genome-enabled prediction in wheat. *G3: Genes| Genomes| Genetics*. 2(12), 1595-1605 (2012).
- 53 Jarquín D, Kocak K, Posadas L, Hyma K, Jedlicka J, Graef G, Lorenz A. Genotyping by sequencing for genomic prediction in a soybean breeding population. *BMC Genomics*. 15(1), 740 (2014).
- 54 Habier D, Fernando R, Dekker J. The impact of genetic relationship information on genome-assisted breeding values. *Genetics*. 177, 2389-2397 (2007).
- 55 Clark S, van der Werf JHJ, Hickey JM. Proceedings of the Association for the Advancement of Animal Breeding and Genetics. 19–21 (2012).
- 56 Clark S, Hickey J, van der Werf JHJ. Different models of genetic variation and their effect on genomic evaluation. *Genet Sel Evol*. 43, 18 (2011).
- 57 Pszczola M, Strabel T, Mulder HA, Calus MPL. Reliability of direct genomic values for animals with different relationships within and to the reference population. *J Dairy Sci*. 95, 389–400 (2012).
- 58 Habier David, Jens Tetens, Franz-Reinhold Seefried, Peter Lichtner, Georg Thaller. The impact of genetic relationship information on genomic breeding values in German Holstein cattle. *Genetics Selection Evolution*. 42:5 (2010).
- 59 Hayes BJ, Visscher PM, Goddard ME. Increased accuracy of artificial selection by using the realized relationship matrix. *Genet. Res*. 91, 47–60 (2009d).
- 60 Goddard ME. Genomic selection: prediction of accuracy and maximization of long-term response. *Genetic*. 136, 245–252 (2009).
- 61 Lorenzana RE, Bernardo R. The accuracy of genotypic value predictions for marker-based selection in bi-parental plant populations. *Theor Appl Genet*. 120(1), 151–161 (2009).
- 62 Heffner EL, Jannink JL, Iwata H, Souza E, and Sorrells ME. Genomic selection accuracy for grain quality traits in biparental wheat populations. *Crop Sci*. 51, 2597–2606 (2011).
- 63 John Hickey M, Susanne Dreisigacker, Jose Crossa, Sarah Hearne, Raman Babu, Boddupalli Prasanna M, Martin Grondona, Vanessa Windhausen S, Andres Zambelli, Mathews Ky, Gregor Gorjanc. Evaluation of genomic selection training population designs and genotyping strategies in plant breeding programs using simulation. *Crop Sci*. 54(4), 1476–1488 (2014).
- 64 Zhang X, Perez-Rodriguez P, Semagn K, Beyene Y, Babu R, Lopez-Cruz MA, San Vicente F, Olsen M, Buckler E, Jannink JL, Prasanna BM, Crossa J. Genomic prediction in biparental tropical maize populations in water-stressed and well-watered environments using low-density and GBS SNPs. *Heredity* 114(3), 291–299 (2015).

Table 1. Genomic heritability (h^2), average predictive ability (r) and accuracy for the seven traits are LD, LDV, SD, SDV, FT10, FT16 and FT22 (*Arabidopsis thaliana*)

	h^2				r				Accuracy			
	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%
LD	0.775	0.752	0.525	0.765	0.857	0.785	0.843	0.697	0.973	0.904	1.163	0.797
LDV	0.72	0.693	0.438	0.713	0.863	0.891	0.893	0.894	1.018	1.07	1.35	1.059
SD	0.772	0.754	0.532	0.759	0.61	0.862	0.832	0.862	0.695	0.993	1.141	0.99
SDV	0.759	0.767	0.489	0.743	0.717	0.898	0.567	0.765	0.823	1.025	0.81	0.887
FT10	0.741	0.724	0.487	0.719	0.619	0.819	0.666	0.788	0.719	0.962	0.954	0.929
FT16	0.764	0.757	0.515	0.733	0.726	0.893	0.873	0.771	0.831	1.038	1.217	0.901
FT22	0.776	0.739	0.53	0.756	0.885	0.867	0.874	0.85	1.004	1.009	1.201	0.978
Mean	0.758	0.741	0.502	0.741	0.754	0.861	0.792	0.804	0.866	1	1.119	0.934

LD: days to flowering under long days; LDV: days to flowering under long days with vernalization; SD: days to flowering under short days; SDV: days to flowering under short days with vernalization; FT10, FT16, and FT22: days of flowering at 10 °C, 16 °C, and 22 °C, respectively.

Table 2. Genomic heritability (h^2), average predictive ability (r) and accuracy for the seven traits are LR, LH, FWR, DWR, and BS (*Soybean datasets with water treatment in 2014 and 2015*)

	h^2				r				Accuracy			
	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%
2014 LR	0.396	0.661	0.625	0.581	0.772	0.632	0.475	0.463	1.226	0.777	0.602	0.607
LH	0.504	0.453	0.395	0.346	0.47	0.42	0.354	0.547	0.662	0.624	0.563	0.931
FWR	0.368	0.501	0.428	0.488	0.128	0.476	0.4	0.298	0.21	0.673	0.612	0.427
DWR	0.419	0.4	0.398	0.364	0.348	0.05	0.335	0.303	0.538	0.079	0.531	0.502
BS	0.481	0.539	0.418	0.444	0.15	0.348	0.541	0.567	0.216	0.474	0.837	0.851
Mean	0.434	0.511	0.453	0.444	0.373	0.385	0.421	0.436	0.57	0.526	0.629	0.664
2015 LR	0.455	0.60	0.564	0.559	0.834	0.698	0.663	0.539	1.236	0.902	0.882	0.721
LH	0.505	0.546	0.564	0.507	0.864	0.577	0.653	0.608	1.216	0.772	0.87	0.854
FWR	0.531	0.63	0.594	0.65	0.896	0.842	0.663	0.708	1.23	1.06	0.86	0.878
DWR	0.464	0.509	0.576	0.466	0.86	0.467	0.655	0.675	1.263	0.655	0.863	0.988
BS	0.387	0.639	0.65	0.65	0.798	0.625	0.801	0.606	1.283	0.782	0.993	0.752
Mean	0.468	0.585	0.59	0.566	0.851	0.64	0.687	0.627	1.246	0.834	0.894	0.839

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table 3. Genomic heritability (h^2), average predictive ability (r) and accuracy for the seven traits are LR, LH, FWR, DWR, and BS (*Soybean data sets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 and 2015*)

	h^2				r				Accuracy			
	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%	All SNPs	5%	10%	20%
2014 LR	0.369	0.583	0.606	0.642	0.875	0.696	0.729	0.575	1.44	0.912	0.937	0.718
LH	0.335	0.437	0.432	0.392	0.742	0.209	0.282	0.383	1.28	0.316	0.428	0.612
FWR	0.421	0.521	0.478	0.525	0.897	0.6	0.487	0.433	1.383	0.831	0.704	0.598
DWR	0.425	0.448	0.423	0.436	0.749	0.548	0.501	0.447	1.149	0.818	0.771	0.677
BS	0.496	0.521	0.537	0.625	0.817	0.297	0.414	0.407	1.16	0.412	0.566	0.514
Mean	0.409	0.502	0.495	0.524	0.816	0.47	0.483	0.449	1.282	0.658	0.681	0.624
2015 LR	0.398	0.551	0.496	0.544	0.909	0.358	0.252	0.374	1.442	0.482	0.357	0.507
LH	0.433	0.559	0.529	0.519	0.694	0.215	0.165	0.205	1.055	0.287	0.227	0.285
FWR	0.5	0.609	0.582	0.586	0.777	0.418	0.517	0.472	1.099	0.535	0.677	0.616
DWR	0.501	0.556	0.661	0.7	0.822	0.364	0.401	0.35	1.16	0.489	0.493	0.418
BS	0.573	0.792	0.747	0.744	0.873	0.601	0.563	0.414	1.153	0.676	0.652	0.48
Mean	0.481	0.613	0.603	0.619	0.815	0.391	0.38	0.363	1.182	0.494	0.481	0.461

LR: main root length; LH: length of hypocotyls of healthy seedlings after treatments with control; FWR: the fresh weights of roots; DWR: dry weights of roots; BS: the biomass of seedlings.

Table 4. Average R^2 and mean absolute error (MAE) across various traits and various numbers of related markers for eight methods (*Arabidopsis thaliana*)

Method	r	R^2	MAE
BayesA	0.798	0.644	0.219
BayesB	0.803	0.655	0.206
BayesC	0.812	0.668	0.200
BLASSO	0.822	0.680	0.220
BRR	0.808	0.659	0.204
GBLUP	0.828	0.700	0.192
RKHS	0.807	0.656	0.168
BLUP	0.828	0.694	0.196

Table 5. Average R^2 and mean absolute error (MAE) across various traits and various numbers of related markers for eight methods (*Soybean datasets with the water treatment in 2014 and 2015*)

Method	r	R^2	MAE
2014 BayesA	0.284	0.116	0.730
BayesB	0.277	0.103	0.721
BayesC	0.307	0.112	0.726
BRR	0.285	0.107	0.722
BLASSO	0.272	0.106	0.718
GBLUP	0.386	0.179	1.008
RKHS	0.308	0.115	0.653
BLUP	0.327	0.130	0.718
2015 BayesA	0.478	0.246	0.748
BayesB	0.509	0.288	0.691
BayesC	0.537	0.299	0.726
BRR	0.556	0.334	0.687
BLASSO	0.529	0.293	0.736
GBLUP	0.646	0.426	0.669
RKHS	0.473	0.239	0.675
BLUP	0.537	0.300	0.710

Table 6. Average R^2 and mean absolute error (MAE) across various traits and various numbers of related markers for eight methods (*Soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014 and 2015*)

Method	r	R^2	MAE
2014 BayesA	0.219	0.083	0.337
BayesB	0.243	0.098	0.340
BayesC	0.223	0.01	0.361
BRR	0.241	0.085	0.353
BLASSO	0.333	0.147	0.323
GBLUP	0.548	0.339	0.314
RKHS	0.361	0.163	0.355
BLUP	0.267	0.106	0.342
2015 BayesA	0.153	0.066	0.586
BayesB	0.174	0.054	0.595
BayesC	0.137	0.046	0.561
BRR	0.177	0.074	0.585
BLASSO	0.319	0.130	0.560
GBLUP	0.473	0.298	0.544
RKHS	0.295	0.108	0.538
BLUP	0.209	0.083	0.551

Fig 1. Boxplots of accuracy and predictive ability (r) for the seven traits across eight methods of genomics prediction under all markers and markers related at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. Boxplots evaluated in different scenarios (i.e., combinations of the trait, the number of SNPs and the training population size). Models include kernel methods (GBLUP, RKHS) and additive methods (BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BLASSO, BRR and BLUP).

Fig 2. Boxplots of accuracy and predictive ability (r) for the five quantitative traits across eight methods of genomics prediction under all markers and markers related at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels in Soybean datasets with water treatment in 2014. Models include kernel methods (GBLUP, RKHS) and additive methods (BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BLASSO, BRR and BLUP).

Fig 3. Boxplots of accuracy and predictive ability (r) for the five quantitative traits across eight methods of genomics prediction under all markers and markers related at the 0.05, 0.10 and 0.20 levels in Soybean datasets with water treatment in 2015. Models include kernel methods (GBLUP, RKHS) and additive methods (BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BLASSO, BRR and BLUP).

Fig 4. Prediction errors (R^2 , and MAE) of the kernel (GBLUP, RKHS) and additive (BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BLASSO, BRR, and BLUP) genomics prediction methods across various traits and various numbers of related markers (*Soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2014*).

Fig 5. Prediction errors (R^2 , and MAE) of the kernel (GBLUP, RKHS) and additive (BayesA, BayesB, BayesC, BLASSO, BRR, and BLUP) genomics prediction methods across various traits and various numbers of related markers (*Soybean datasets with the salt (NaCl) treatment in 2015*).

Dr. Medrine Mmayi Odinga

meldymmayi@gmail.com

State Key Laboratory of Crop Genetics and Germplasm Enhancement,
Nanjing Agricultural University,
Nanjing 210095

© 2022 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

Author(s) have identified their affiliated institutions or organizations, along with the corresponding country or geographic region. NAAR, TWASP remains neutral with regard to any jurisdictional claims.

